

Tabla. Compendio de estudios primarios resultado de la búsqueda.

Id	Artículo	N.C	Año	Ref.
E1	An Approach for Rapid Source Code Development Based on ChatGPT and Prompt engineering	19	2024	[21]
E2	Self-collaboration code generation via chatgpt	301	2024	[22]
E3	Generating Java code pairing with ChatGPT	3	2024	[1]
E4	An Empirical Study of the Non-determinism of ChatGPT in Code Generation	64	2025	[23]
E5	From Misuse to Mastery: Enhancing Code Generation with Knowledge-Driven AI Chaining	32	2023	[8]
E6	Prompt Problems: A New Programming Exercise for the Generative AI Era	141	2024	[24]
E7	Developing time series forecasting models with generative large language models	5	2024	[7]
E8	Enhancing robustness of AI offensive code generators via data augmentation	6	2025	[25]
E9	ANPL: towards natural programming with interactive decomposition	11	2024	[3]
E10	Knowledge-Aware Code Generation with Large Language Models	16	2024	[26]
E11	RGD: Multi-LLM Based Agent Debugger via Refinement and Generation Guidance	2	2024	[2]
E12	A study on prompt design, advantages and limitations of ChatGPT for deep learning program repair	95	2025	[10]
E13	CodeDoctor: multi-category code review comment generation	1	2025	[27]
E14	LLM-Based Multi-Agent Systems for Software Engineering: Literature Review, Vision and the Road Ahead	27	2025	[14]
E15	"It's Weird That it Knows What I Want": Usability and Interactions with Copilot for Novice Programmers	228	2023	[6]

Acronimos usados: Id = Identificador del Estudio, NC = Número de Citaciones, Ref. = Referencias.